

Critical fitting: pedagogy for confronting colonial dynamics in fashion

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Olivia Hegarty,² London College of Fashion, University of the Arts, London, United Kingdom

Cian O'Donovan, Department of Science and Technology Studies, University College London, UK

Sara Chong Kwan, London College of Fashion, University of the Arts London, UK

Luke Stevens, London College of Fashion, University of the Arts, London, UK; Ranra Studios, UK

Abstract

The simplification and standardisation of fit is critical to fashion's ability to sell, ship and scale products globally. These processes are facilitated in part by vocational teaching which ties fit to harmful colonial dynamics in industry. Critical fitting is a methodology for staging opportunities for students to confront these dynamics in classrooms by encouraging them to foreground their own sensory embodied knowledge of fit. This article traces its pedagogical, methodological and conceptual development at London College of Fashion. Outlined are playful but conceptually powerful strategies used to recall and imagine alternative material-practices and ways of knowing – from those predetermined in industrially-produced garments to those enacted by the hands of participants' grandmothers.

We contribute to Science and Technology Studies scholarship in three ways. Pedagogically, we show how small changes in technical routines can redistribute epistemic authority in classrooms and open space for decolonial practices without presupposing a discursive decolonial frame.

Methodologically we introduce critical fitting as a compositional and sensory-embodied intervention that renders tacit, world-specific, bodily know-how present. Conceptually we reframe fit as an ontological concern rather than a 'one-world' assumption sedimented in technical practice that is traditionally open only to critiques of representation and measurement.

Keywords

colonial modernity, critical pedagogy, design, fashion, sensory embodied methods

Introduction: the case of fit

Fit is how a garment interacts with the body wearing it. Orthodox design teaching ties fit to industrial and western cultural norms via technical practices that facilitate speed and scale. The teaching of these technical practices come at a cost. Preparing students to fit into jobs, design educators enact industry standards, excluding the knowledge and experiences of students that might challenge industry norms or open up alternative possibilities for fashion's futures.

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² **Corresponding author:** o.hegarty@arts.ac.uk, London College of Fashion, 105 Carpenter's Road London, E20 2AR, UK. +44 (0)20 7514 7400.

We identify *fit*, a core concept in fashion practice, as a site for confronting harmful industrial practices in fashion education. Our contribution to Science and Technology Studies is three-fold: 1) Pedagogically we show how small changes in technical routines can redistribute epistemic authority in classrooms. 2) In those classrooms we use sensory embodied methods to make bodily know-how present and discussable. 3) Conceptually we reframe fit as an ontological concern rather than an issue of representation and measurement. Drawing together these insights we propose critical fitting, a methodology for confronting colonial dynamics in fashion and other cultural-industrial domains.

We situate this challenge as one of confronting enduring practices (Tuck and Yang 2012) and dynamics (Arora and van Dyck 2025; Arora and Stirling 2023) that constitute colonial modernity (Quijano 2011; 2007; Jansen 2020).³ We employ this concept to grasp entrenched colonial relations underpinning dominant worldmaking practices (Arora and Stirling 2023). Fashion is intimately tied to these dynamics: it is deeply integrated with economic and cultural extraction and subjugation of people, regions, resources and knowledges (Bartlett 2019; Liboiron 2021; Earthsight 2024; Niessen 2020). This worldmaking works both ways. Colonial modernity is also at 'the very core of [fashion's] constitution... falsely claiming universality' (Jansen 2020, 815). Niessen calls for a redefinition of fashion, critically questioning its very existence so long as it continues to be understood in its own historical terms as 'a signal and expression of European superiority' (Niessen 2020, 862).

Curricula in fashion schools prioritise 'universal' garment archetypes such as the European men's shirt, that model shape and fit on the body as 'built-in' through standardised industrial processes. Because design features that evolved in European settings such as sewn darts, shaping in seams, and complex construction details (e.g. cuffs, collars), do not feature in archetypes such as the sari and wrapper, those garments are often excluded from technical training in garment design. When *non-Eurocentric* garments are excluded from the classroom, so too are the hands of wearers tying, folding and knotting fabrics into place along with the tacit knowledge in bodily techniques and sensory responses learned over generations.

Here we see the production of what Law calls the one-world world (2015): the erasure of these garment-types from the canon also erases the complex knowledge-entanglements that orthodox education boxes off as 'cultural', 'historical' or even 'agricultural'. For instance, the world of a cotton sari, made from a single piece of often treasured cloth, without cuts or seams is enacted through understandings of raw material provenance. Appreciations of the socio-material complexity of growing, spinning and weaving processes are embedded in this world, along with the cotton grower's tacit knowledge of weather patterns and the dyer's botanical expertise. Social know-how of wearing the sari is also embedded in its world, like the significance of the last wrap of fabric going over the shoulder towards the back or towards the front. Fashion educators bring these points about the sari into the classroom as cultural history. But as separate categories of 'nature' and 'culture' they make little sense in the sari's world. This is where, even in promoting cultural diversity, education reinforces nature/culture divides and a bifurcation of non-European garments as 'non-fashion' (Niessen 2020).

³ Given their diverse social-material and world-building forms, colonial modernity's constituting features are often approached as ontological in STS (Law 2015; Cadena and Blaser 2018; Arora and Stirling 2023).

Our challenge in this research was to try to keep these worlds intact in the classroom. We did this by disturbing fit - a practice at the heart of how fashion is taught and produced. Fit allows us to confront colonial dynamics in a practical way - focussing the relations, intersubjectivities and contexts in which fit happens and by which contemporary colonial practices are reproduced. Our work builds upon radical proposals to re-conceive fashion design education as 'otherwise' (Williams 2024, 6) and research that scrutinises tools of technical education using decolonial thinking (Ahmed 2022).

This case of fit reports on a four year enquiry into decolonising fashion pedagogy at London College of Fashion (LCF), where three of us teach and where the making of physical garments and prototypes are core to learning objectives on design modules. To succeed on these modules, students must learn to practice entangled industry-scholarly ideas of good fit. In this case we problematise orthodox processes of good fit and suggest alternative practices and pedagogy.

Fit is achieved through practices of fitting

At LCF these practices happen in fitting tutorials. Whether a garment fits or not is appraised visually, looking out for dragging or stretched fabric, checking material performs the designer's intent. Fit functionality is tested through movement, e.g. restrictions in walking. Teaching fit in this way prepares students for professional life - to design with industrial manufacturing systems built with international sizing standards. In industry fittings, a fit model, usually chosen for their waist, hips and chest measurements matching standardised mannequins, tries on prototypes allowing the designer and team to make stylistic and technical decisions. Tacit, analytic and sensorial knowledge produced by the wearer in fittings is rarely collected as part of the design process.

Two issues are at stake. Unreflexive adherence to industry standards means that in fitting sessions, not everyone fits. Paying attention to categories and subjectivities of race, body size, shape and the inclusion of disabled people, activist educators and students have made significant progress towards diversifying who gets to be represented in fittings (Barry and Christel 2023; *The Fashion and Race Database* 2024; Williams 2021).

Yet this valuable critical work does not address a second issue: what fashion *is* or *can be* in an ontological sense. This is because ideas of fit run deeper than comparing and calibrating the measure of garments against even more diversely representative bodies. In the classroom the ontological possibilities offered by fit are rarely up-for-grabs.

The 'sensory revolution' in fashion studies offers a way forward, incorporating phenomenological (Merleau-Ponty [1945] 1962) and sensory ethnographic (Pink 2009) methodologies to articulate the body-senses-material entanglements, where senses are treated both as the object of study and the means of inquiry.⁴

Combining sensory embodied methods with discursive methods invites a process of action and reflection (Freire 1970); to reflect on the corporeal experience of being clothed in the social world; on how the body feels when dressed; and how it moves in space. This has material implications for the construction and negotiation of identity and subjectivities, as well

⁴ Sensory Studies has established through a vast body of anthropological work which 'involves a cultural approach to the study of the senses and a sensory approach to the study of culture' (Howes 2005), that multiple sensoriums (sensory worlds and cultures) exist across time and place, demonstrating that the senses are not biologically determined nor universally fixed. Within cultures, 'the senses are imbued with meaning and carefully hierarchized and regulated so as to express and enforce the social and cosmic order' (Howes 2005, 3).

as the positioning of people and practices within the social world [author's prior study, details withheld for review].

In textbooks and classrooms, the exclusion of epistemologies of indigenous peoples manifests as a form of dominance that delegitimises non-Eurocentric ways of knowing and marginalises students who value them (Cech et al. 2017). To confront this, and to legitimise the knowledge and values of all students in the classroom, we use sensory embodied methods as a form of knowledge-making critical pedagogy.

Our research question is: how can sensory embodied methods confront constituting colonial dynamics in fashion education?

Methods

Practice-based students at London College of Fashion are taught reflective, multi-method approaches (Schön 1983; Bulley and Sahin 2021). This pedagogy provided a methodological entry point. It was through the *doing of fit* and particularly the *feeling of fitting* in practice-based teaching that we wanted to bring to classrooms a 'world of many worlds' (Cadena and Blaser 2018).

To foreground ontological concerns, we composed a problem space around fitting practices. Lury's articulation of an unbounded problem space usefully describes how our understanding of the problem and the development of the methodology evolved in tandem, 'compulsively composed' (2021, 6).

We composed the critical fitting intervention following a relational mapping analysis of technical teaching in fashion, mapping the practices, tools, discourses that 'matter' in fittings (Clarke et al. 2018, 104). Over the course of 15 workshops from 2022 to 2024, we adapted the activity, continually reconfiguring the problem and designing appropriate interventions (a visual essay illustrates this process: Chong Kwan et al. 2025). Analytically our job was not to arrive at a definitive situational map of entities but to consider the ontological implications of the new bodies, subjectivities, and knowledges in the problem space.

Reported data comes from two workshops. In September 2023 at a fashion education conference in Berlin we recruited 10 educators from European design schools via a call to conference attendees. In June 2024 we convened 14 LCF educators, students and alumni. Educational levels of student attendees covered BA, MA and PhD and non-staff were paid. A globally diverse range of ethnicities and nationalities were represented across the two workshops and participants were majority female. We did not boost recruitment for gender or other characteristics, however composition was reflective of student and staff demographics at LCF. Institutional ethics clearance was granted by research offices in LCF/UAL and research with students was reviewed as part of a UAL Teaching and Learning Fund grant awarding process.

The critical fitting

We elaborate three moments of in-situ composition using vignettes to illustrate sensorial knowledge-making. We show how critical fitting prompts opened-up classroom situations to the possibility of onto-epistemic shifts.

Prompt: Ask the wearer how they feel

On a sunny September afternoon, coats and bags were left behind by two workshop groups as they set off on a short walk from the UdK Berlin conference building close to the

Landwehrkanal. A member of each group dressed themselves with an abstract garment large enough to wear over their clothes (Figure 1). Even for fashion educators it was not obvious how the garments should be worn. The shapes were not recognisable as everyday clothing archetypes yet they felt somewhat familiar, with edges finished as clothing details. Nevertheless, the groups did not hesitate to try on their garments in a variety of modes: up, down, tied, folded and hanging over shoulders.

Figure 1. Abstract garments ready for use in a critical fitting workshop, Berlin. When laid flat they are asymmetrical shapes with protruding edges that could become fastening ties via knotting. The garment patterns were created by participants at preceding workshops and then fabricated as toiles by workshop organisers. See workshop design guidelines at criticalfitting.com. Image courtesy of the authors.

One group stopped in a courtyard. A group-member used their Posca-pen to write 'Permission !?' on the garment worn by a fellow-walker, then adding: "thank you for allowing me to fit".

Alongside pens, groups had been given a pouch containing fitting tools: tailor's chalk, snips, safety pins, clips as well as a pack of prompt cards. This group had chosen the 'Senses' pack and just before this moment, had read out the instruction: "Ask the wearer how they feel?". The cards prompted groups to take action while wearing the garment. For instance: "Secure the garment close to the body. Take a walk". Each action was followed-up by a discussion prompt such as "Where did you learn this technique?". They captured their discussion through writing, drawing or mark-making directly onto the garments as they were worn.

This group, happily carrying out familiar actions of dressing and fitting their group-mate, went to record their comments on the worn garment. Then they paused. A team-member suggested they first check with the wearer if this was ok.

For fashion educators, tactile operations in dressing others are common practice. Asking a passive fit-model about their feelings is not. In this situation however, the focus on sensory engagement created a shift in whose knowledge mattered. By moving from a visual assessment to asking how the garment felt, participants recognised the sensory experience of the wearer, bringing their knowledge into the situation.

Later we gathered on the canal bank near Marchbrücke. Participant 2 told us:

"the garments (or like whatever it is), really facilitated the discussion and I feel when you fit something, it's always really separated... from the designer and the model and then the product ... the three separate things. Whereas in this walk, I feel it was like an embedded experience and ... you could really experience from the body perspective and from the dresser perspective and from the wearer perspective."

Prompt: Does wearing the garment in this way bring back any memories? Tell us a story?

Along the Landwehrkanal one group drew a prompt card to "Free the garment from the body". Our field notes capture subsequent conversation and movements.

"Noticed different heights of wearer

Made it like wings – moving arms

...

Expressed annoyance at lack of agency with normal clothes – why so prescriptive?" (Figure 2)

Figure 2. A participant marking up the garment as it is worn during the critical fitting at Berlin fashion education conference Digital Multilogue, September 2023. Image courtesy of the authors.

The group documented the comfort afforded by less fitted ways of wearing the garments: “PONCHONESS = GOOD”. This garment had zips and straps, the group could have constructed some jacket or ‘universal’ archetype. Instead they celebrated the poncho, an archetype missing from the canon of patterncutting fundamentals, because it does not demonstrate fit.

The group stopped often, rearranging, tying sections through legs, making a belt around the waist, cutting into parts to make pockets. Different participants tried it on; they walked into shops and engaged with passers-by. Afterwards they wrote:

“WHEN IS FIT FINISHED?”

HOW DOES IT MAKE US FIT IN?”

By contrast, the other group found an arrangement of wearing their garment that relied on the presence of a recognisable fastening detail: a partial placket (shirt front buttonstand) without collar or other shirt features. During the walk, this detail landed on the front of the body and the group wrote:

“LOOKS like it belongs” near the placket detail.

The reaction to the placket landing in the ‘right’ place hints at the complexity of embedded colonial relations in codes of dressing and conventional fashion practices. These interactions spurred questions for us when we mapped the situation later. Are there features that ‘belong’ and ‘do not belong’ on clothed bodies? Does this suggest a prevalence of Euro-American standards and their embedded values: a one-world ontology? What garments and what worlds fit outside those boundaries?

In other workshops we saw connections between dressing practices and knowledge worlds. Prompts encouraged participant insights from a point of deep knowledge of being-in-a-body through the practices of dressing and moving. One prompt generated numerous reflections: “Does wearing the garment in this way bring back any memories? Tell us a story?” At an STS conference workshop, a participant with Mexican indigenous heritage spoke of their grandmother’s dressing practices teaching us about garment archetypes from that place - notable in part because the knowledge of grandmothers is not usually discussed in the context of academia. A Peruvian participant shared dressmaking methods that used bodily actions in place of measuring tapes. A British participant talked about their Caribbean grandmother who, after emigrating to London, commissioned tailored clothing and enjoyed wearing a well-fitting suit: an important signifier that she ‘fit in’ to British society.

Prompt: Does this action relate to embodied ways of knowing?

During the final session of the 2024 London workshop, groups gathered to discuss the day’s activities. Reflecting on a workshop garment, participant 8 said:

‘It’s a bit more open-ended, it’s an intuitive sort of fitting, you’re sort of confronted with something you’ve never seen before and you don’t have a specific outcome or garment or archetype that you’re working towards, you’re sort of just making it up as you go along with things that you’ve known from the past or things you can reference... it was a bit more of a freeing task ... learning new things on the spot as opposed to trying to achieve something’

Rather than working towards a predetermined outcome, staff and student participants felt their way, actively and critically, through fitting clothes and discussing, paying attention to what their hands and bodies were doing and feeling. Sensing and making-sense-of drew out embodied understandings that were *felt*, but were less straightforwardly articulated.

Earlier, groups cut into fabric we had pre-printed with wording from assignment briefs. They used sewing skills to emphasise or hide phrases in the brief (Figure 3). Participant 11 said:

‘It was, at one point, a garment, and then it was... an artefact... it became [like] a scrunched up piece of paper.. I think the fluidity between the contexts was really important... that freedom to transcend boundaries and limitations.’

Figure 3. A member of teaching staff cuts and stitches learning outcomes during the decolonising workshop. Image courtesy of the authors.

Participants acknowledged that during the workshop making activities, (*doing* fashion processes such as handling material, using their bodies and playing) led them to think about what fashion *can be* and what fashion *can do*.

Participant 4 - a recent graduate - reflected on their own transition to an industry job:

'It's quite hard when you do this kind of thing as a student, to then go into to industry where they might see it as a box which they haven't cut up and they're not willing to chop and change it or twist or fold it and then yours

is... it doesn't fit anymore.. and that maybe is a disconnect... between university and when you come out of it.'

Cutting, chopping, twisting, folding were hands-on processes used by participants for producing knowledge and shifting the boundaries of fashion worlds. These were familiar practices, yet participants noted a *misfit* between working with hands-on creative practices in university where process is more important versus the fixed, outcome-orientated ways of designing in workplace settings.

Discussion

Pedagogy: re-distributing epistemic authority

The workshops demonstrated how a small change in a *technical* routine (the fitting tutorial) can redistribute epistemic authority in design education, opening space for decolonial practices without presupposing a discursive decolonial frame.

Our analysis of orthodox fitting situations revealed an absence of the fit-model's sensory knowledge - striking, given the centrality of the body in these processes. This accords with decolonial scholarship on senses: worlds that undergo colonial transformations experience the loss of senses and importantly the loss of memory of the senses (Seremetakis 1994, 8). The senses are integral to the embedding and universalisation of colonial modernity: enlightenment 'politics of knowledge was grounded in the suppression of sensing and the body and of its geo-historical location. It was precisely that suppression that made it possible for both [of these politics] of knowledge to claim universality' (Mignolo 2011, 274–75).

In the workshops, we saw how participants' sensory capacities created knowledge through *sensation* and *making sense*: 'a reaching out to the world as a source of information and an understanding of the world so gathered' (Vannini et al. 2012, 123). Through the sense-making of embodied experiences, participants challenged the prescribed canon by attending to their own values. In the LCF workshop students objected to frequent use in class of the term 'industry standards' asking how can this be code for 'best practice' when so much is known of industry harms?

Here we see alignment with critical pedagogy which encourages students to put into classroom discussions their own lived experience (hooks 1994). Critical fitting is not a didactic tool for bringing explicit decolonial discourse into the fashion classroom. The decolonial act is in centring participants' embodied knowledge and there are no guarantees that coloniality will be discussed. Freirean teaching holds that personal transformations occur as students benefit from the empowerment of valuing their own lived experience. We found that the critical reflection offered by the fitting activities opened space for participants to draw in experiences of colonial dynamics in education and beyond. In our 2024 London workshop Participant 1, a Black Caribbean British woman, said:

'It's about London recognising the responsibility they have now... it's not just about being inclusive of people around you, but it's about the countries that they have taken from How do you give back to them, how do you bring them in, and make their opinions and their skills, and their knowledge part of this whole fashion world?'

These contributions brought into the classroom colonial histories of London which are embedded in the lived experiences of many British students with heritage from former

colonies. These knowledges sit outside the 'canon of fashion's Euromerican normativity' (Jansen 2020, 825). Many student-designers, British and international, come to London to learn to design a world that in-turn erases their own knowledge-worlds: 'we design our world, while our world acts back on us and designs us' (Willis 2006, 70).

Methodology: making bodily know-how present

By transgressing industry and educational norms intended to achieve a 'well-fitting' garment, workshop participants engaged in a world-building enquiry with open-ended objectives. This directed creative critical capacities towards the undercritiqued 'technical' curriculum. Through practice and attention to existing embodied skills (Ingold 2000), participants challenged assumptions that there are no alternatives for fashion outside of modernity.

The open-ended making processes shown in the third vignette echo the world-building practices of design more broadly in its 'reorientation from production to knowledge creation' (Redström 2020, 89). In the shift from craft to machine-making, the purpose of design shifted. Prototyping opens possibilities for an exploratory mode of design, unconstrained by the limits of making at scale. While on the one hand, design sits firmly inside modernity, it can also disrupt relations of colonial modernity by offering possibilities for building new ontologies as it 'rethink(s) its relation to the object' (Michael 2012, 172). Designers can *do* praxis and *do* poietic by 'engaging with the nature of what design practice helps bring into being' (Schultz et al. 2018, 83).

Critical fitting differs from existing design research methods in its retooling of a specific technical routine (the fitting) into an ontological intervention that contests industrial archetypes and their embedded colonial dynamics. While sharing a disposition towards world-building with critical design and speculative design in its use of design methods to 'question prevailing values' (Dunne and Raby 2013, 44; see also Malpass 2013), critical fitting gets closer to participants' sensory lifeworlds (Pink 2009, 50). It uses in-the-moment sensory action rather than projected imaginary scenarios to reveal plural worlds already present but excluded from the situation.

There are overlaps in critical fitting's centring of the wearer's experience with participatory design and co-design methodologies where the end user works collaboratively to design according to their needs (Bannon and Ehn 2012, 76). Our method differs however - there is no intended design outcome. Through open-ended action, participants challenge whether fit can or should be 'designed' or taught, asking to what purpose and whose benefit.

Given the decolonial foundations of the work, a closer alignment might be with participatory action research (McNiff 2013) or variants on educational action research where practitioner-researchers aim to sustain change (Noffke and Somekh 2009). In critical fitting, drawing from the inclinations of situational analysis, we map the change-making motivations of ourselves as researchers into the situation. Rather than monitoring and analysing the change-making, we compose a situation that reveals socio-material entanglements, allowing possibilities for change to occur. Our positionality as critical pedagogues tells us *which way to look, but not what to see* (reworking Clarke et al. 2018, 93).

Theory: re-framing technical routines

Critical fitting tested Mignolo's adage that 'you do not see coloniality, but there is no way you cannot sense it' (2018, 372). Conceptually we reframed fit as an ontological concern. Our interventions were a way of problematizing and situating colonial modernity. Sensing and

sense-making were brought together as a means of locating colonially accumulated power and privilege - without the need to first identify discursive formations of coloniality. Inclusive practices intended to broaden the scope of who is represented within fashion systems sideline ontological concerns over which fashion practices were enacted and how (Mol 2002). For instance, fashion journalists have celebrated the benefits efforts to address representation in curricula have brought to industry: diversity helps sell more goods (Shoaib 2022). Mignolo (after Mahbubani 2002) calls these kinds of moves 'de-westernization' rather than decolonial, which rest on the 'principle that the *regeneration* of life shall prevail over primacy of the *production and reproduction* of goods at the cost of life' (2009, 161 italics in original). Moreover, they leave colonial dynamics such as extraction, exploitation and appropriation undisturbed.

Bodies are of obvious importance to thinking and doing fashion. All practices are embodied after all. By placing sensorial embodied knowledge at the heart of a problem space or research situation, sensory embodied methods might complement approaches to confronting epistemic authority in speculative knowledge (Adams et al. 2009; Guston 2014; Hilgartner et al. 2015; Jasanoff and Kim 2009) as a way to access plural ontologies. This is especially relevant in fields already open to phenomenological approaches and that understand ontologies as enacted through practices such as STS inquiries in healthcare and crip HCI (Jensen 2010; Mol et al. 2011; Forlano 2023; Robins et al. 2025). For instance, using prompts and sensory activities to shift what's scrutinised in a clinical training lab, towards technical routines and expert knowledge.

Limitations

What it *feels* like to fit fabric to the body cannot easily be datified or documented where body and world are 'continually being made and re-made' (Negrin 2015, 116–19). To mitigate, we asked participants to make notes on garments while worn. In analysing the flat, bodiless garments later, the comments and marks re-ignited, for us researchers, moments of participant knowledge-production. We cross-referenced these with field notes and images of the movements and actions. Field notes were more valuable than initially anticipated in capturing nuance between actions and discussion.

Aligning with 'vitalist' methodologies, we acknowledge that the researcher may only 'glimpse' participants' lifeworlds but never fully know. Experiential *data* is animated, moving and always becoming (Vannini 2026, 8).

The impact of our intervention on students, as an emancipatory form of critical pedagogy, cannot be easily ascertained because it sits in a wider curriculum alongside other influences. Moreover, the contribution of this case to decolonial transformation at LCF is modest. However, its importance is in how it opens up a new conceptual pathway for ongoing transformational efforts.

Conclusions

Our research question was 'how can sensory embodied methods confront constituting colonial dynamics in fashion education?' Our workshops show how ocularcentric articulations of industry-standard fitting practices suppress the agency of the wearer in sense-making (Negrin 2015, 115). In response, we demonstrated how fit can be operationalised in educational practice to promote ontological pluralism rather than settling for representational diversity. The stories that emerged in workshops showed how embodied practice-based methods can evoke embedded and hidden knowledge - an onto-epistemic

knowing-through-being (Verran 2014). Compositional intervention brought tacit knowledges and their related worlds into technical spaces normally shielded from decolonial critique.

A small shift in classroom knowledge production has wider implications for building new ontologies of fashion. This opportunity exists alongside an enduring challenge for fashion activist educators who balance responsibilities to students with projects to decolonise industry. Without recognising that orthodox fashion practices are constituent of *one* unacknowledged ontology - modernity - projects committed to decolonising curricula may remain only partially realised.

Constructing a Science and Technology Studies-infused problem space, a small onto-epistemic shift made in the situation allows fashion educators to use design tools to make space for change. STS critiques of design have challenged designers to bring forward new tools for new practices rather than merely generate novel design outcomes that do little to restructure unjust design relations and interdependencies (Benjamin 2019; Escobar 2011). Our work stages an opportunity for design education to make visible the shaping of realities and subjectivities, not just products.

Returning one last time to the case of fit, sites of accepted knowledge-production for educational settings here move away from text-books, journal articles, domain histories and industrial processes to the lived experience and personal and intersubjective histories of the learners in the room. When knowledge is considered in this way, we end up shifting what Mignolo calls 'the geography of reason' (2009, 172). This situated knowledge confronts the exclusions enacted by a one-world world and opens up the possibility of welcoming many worlds into our classrooms.

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The data and research reported here was gathered and conducted in line with University of the Arts London Code of Practice on Educational and Research Ethics. All study participants physically signed informed consent statements and these statements have been retained.

Data availability statement

Ahead of publication, a repository of anonymised photographs of garments, sensory embodied practices and workshop tools will be made available at an appropriate online repository. Other data collected includes workshop photographs of participants, audio recordings, annotated garments and personal notes, along with audio transcripts and analytic notes. These data are not appropriate to make available due to the nature of the ethical consent agreed with participants.

Orcid

Olivia Hegarty <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-4912-1214>

Cian O'Donovan <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4467-9687>

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